

Continuous Certificate Evaluation

- User Manual -

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1. Introduction

The *Continuous Certification Evaluation (CCE)* component of MEDINA collects assessment results and builds an evaluation tree representing the aggregated assessment results on higher levels of the certification scheme to determine compliance with the different certification elements.

The evaluation of security compliance in MEDINA starts with the gathering of evidence by different tools and techniques. Security assessment components assess this evidence based on the target values as configured for the specific requirement and provide their output (assessment results with the state of fulfilment of a specific metric for a specific monitored resource) to the *Continuous Certification Evaluation (CCE)* component. If the assessment result value represents the lowest-level information about the certification state, the role of the CCE component is to combine the received assessment results into information about the fulfilment of higher-level certification objects: requirements, controls, control groups, and the selected certificate scheme in its entirety. This information does not directly determine the cloud service's eligibility for a certificate, but serves as input for other components, the *Risk Assessment and Optimisation Framework (RAOF)*¹ and the *Certificate Lifecycle Manager (LCM)*², as well as for easy visualisation of the certificate state for the users (Cloud Service Providers - CSPs and auditors).

1.1. User Roles and Permissions

Access to CCE is managed by Keycloak³. The visibility of the different elements of the *Continuous Certification Evaluation (CCE)*, and the operations that are allowed to be carried out, are conditioned by the role to which each authenticated user is assigned.

The table below details which actions are allowed for each of the defined roles:

Roles	Allowed Actions
IT Security Governance	Read the evaluation tree
Security Analyst	Read the evaluation tree
Domain Governance	Read the evaluation tree
Product and Service Owner	Read the evaluation tree
Product (Security) Engineer	Read the evaluation tree
Chief Information Security Office (CISO)	Read the evaluation tree
Customer	None
Auditor	Read the evaluation tree

¹ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D4.5 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927237>

² For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D4.3 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927231>

³ <https://www.keycloak.org>

2. User Manual

2.1. Toolbar

The *Continuous Certification Evaluation (CCE)* includes a toolbar (see Figure 1), always accessible in the upper area, with all the options that are available in the tool:

Figure 1. CCE toolbar

The different menu options, which are described in the following sections, are as follows:

- **Evaluation overview:** Provides an aggregated view of compliant and non-compliant resources and requirements for all cloud services.
- **Evaluation tree:** Provides a graphical representation of the evaluation tree for each cloud service, showing detailed information about the assessments results.
- **Help:** Provides access to the user manual.

2.2. Evaluation overview

The *Evaluation overview* menu option (see Figure 2) provides an overview of compliant and non-compliant resources and requirements for all cloud services.

Cloud Service Name	Target of Evaluation	Resources Total	Resources Compliant	Resources Non-compliant	Requirements Total	Requirements Compliant	Requirements Non-compliant
MichelaCS2	MichelaCS2 : EUCS	0			998		
Bosch_SaaS	Bosch_SaaS : EUCS	0			998		
AlwaysGreenExceptOne	AlwaysGreenExceptOne : EUCS	71	71 ↑	0 ↓	1996	71 ↑	0 ↓
AlwaysGreen	AlwaysGreen : EUCS	71	71 ↑	0 →	1996	71 ↑	0 →
Bosch Cloud Service	Bosch Cloud Service : EUCS	0			998		
Bosch_PaaS	Bosch_PaaS : EUCS	16	9 →	7 →	1996	3 →	1 →
Bosch_IaaS	Bosch_IaaS : EUCS	39	9 →	30 ↑	1996	3 →	4 →
AlwaysRed	AlwaysRed : EUCS	71	0 →	71 ↑	1996	0 →	71 ↑

Figure 2. CCE Evaluation overview

On the left side is the list of cloud service and their Targets of evaluation. The Target of Evaluation (ToE) binds a cloud service to a certification framework (or catalogue). The right side shows total, compliant, and non-compliant resources and requirements.

Each compliant and non-compliant value also has a coloured arrow. There are three types of arrows:

- 1) Arrow up means that the number of compliant or non-compliant resources or requirements is increasing in relation to last couple of assessment result.
- 2) Arrow down means the number of compliant or non-compliant resources or requirements is decreasing in relation to last couple of assessment result.
- 3) Arrow to the right (in black colour) means the number of compliant or non-compliant resources or requirements has not changed from the last couple of assessment result.

The colour of the arrow indicates if the change is positive (green) or negative (red).

2.3. Evaluation tree

The *Evaluation tree* menu option (see Figure 3) provides a graphical representation of the evaluation tree for each cloud service, with detailed information about assessments results for the selected cloud service.

Figure 3. CCE Evaluation tree

2.3.1. Navigation toolbar

The *Navigation toolbar* option (see Figure 4) enables the user to move around and to interact with the evaluation tree using the following buttons.

Figure 4. Navigation toolbar

- 1) **Select Target of Evaluation:** if a user has access to multiple Targets of Evaluation, they can switch between them with the drop-down menu on the top left (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Select Target of Evaluation

- 2) **History:** the top-right button enables to user to review the history (past results) for each selected Target of Evaluation (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. History

3) **Zoom in:** enables to zoom in on the current part of the tree (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. Zoom in

4) **Zoom out:** enables to zoom out to see an entire tree (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Zoom out

- 5) **Reset zoom:** sets zoom to the default value, i.e., the value used when the tree is first displayed.
- 6) **Collapse all:** removes all nodes and shows only the highest node (security framework) (see Figure 9).

Figure 9. Collapse all

- 7) **Expand all:** shows all nodes in a tree like structure, expanding from the security framework to Control groups, Controls, Requirements, Resources and Metrics (see Figure 10).

Figure 10. Expand all

- 8) **Show yellow nodes:** yellow nodes (no assessment results) are shown by default. Unticking the box hides yellow nodes and leaves only compliant (green) and non-compliant (red) nodes (see Figure 11).

Figure 11. Show yellow nodes

9) **Instructions:** provides information on how to manipulate the nodes (left click: hide/show child nodes; right click: permanently open node details).

2.3.2. Tree view

The user can move the tree by holding down the left mouse button and moving the mouse. By left-clicking on the node, the user can show or hide child nodes. Right clicking on a node permanently opens an additional window with details of the node (see Figure 13 and Figure 13). This window also opens temporary when hovering the mouse over the node.

Figure 12. Example of the details of a Requirement node

Figure 13. Example of the details of a Resource node

3. Delivery and usage

3.1. Licensing information

This component is offered under Apache 2.0 license. The license files and more detailed information can be found in the MEDINA Public GitLab repository⁴.

3.2. Download

The code of the component is available at the public GitLab repository of the MEDINA project:

- CCE back-end (core): <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/continuous-certification-evaluation>
- CCE front-end (web UI): <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/cce-frontend>
- Java library for communication with the *Catalogue of Controls and Metrics*⁵: <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/catalogue-client-java>
- Java library for communication with the *Orchestrator*⁶: <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/orchestrator-client-java>

3.3. More information

Interested readers can find more information about the *Continuous Certificate Evaluation* at this link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927231> “D4.3 Tools and Techniques for the Management and Evaluation of Cloud Security Certifications – v3”.

The MEDINA web site (<https://medina-project.eu/>) also includes several deliverables and blog posts related to the *Continuous Certificate Evaluation* component.

⁴ <https://git.code.tecnalia.com/medina/public/continuous-certification-evaluation>

⁵ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D2.2 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7794478>

⁶ For more detailed information about this component, the interested reader is referred to the MEDINA Deliverable D3.6 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7927225>